
TOXICITY STUDIES - AN OVERVIEW

Nithya.M¹, Manivannan.R², Abinaya.R³, Dhanush.K. P³, Pavithra.M³,
Tamilselvan.S³, Vimalya.S³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Excel College of Pharmacy, Komarapalayam,
Namakkal -637303, Tamilnadu, India, nithi.m96@gmail.com.

²Professor & Principal, Department of Pharmaceutics, Excel College of Pharmacy, Komarapalayam,
Namakkal -637303, Tamilnadu, India.

³B.Pharm Final Year Students, Excel College of Pharmacy, Komarapalayam,
Namakkal -637303, Tamilnadu, India.

ABSTRACT

Toxicity testing is critical in the evaluation of novel medications before they are used on humans. The goal of toxicity testing is to identify any potential hazardous consequences that a test chemical may have, not merely to determine how safe it is. The main goals of toxicity testing are to determine how test compounds affect lab animals and whether they have any direct hazardous effects on humans. Secondly, high doses of test substances are given to lab animals in order to assess any potential risks to humans who receive much lower levels. The current review aims to highlight the importance of toxicity testing. Toxicity testing is of the following types: Acute toxicity studies, sub-acute toxicity studies, and chronic toxicity studies are the three different categories of toxicity testing. A variety of tests were used in animal species for toxicity testing, including long-term drug administration, regular monitoring of physiological and biochemical abnormalities, and a thorough post-mortem examination at the conclusion of the trial to look for obvious or histological abnormalities. Because animals are useful for studying a functioning organism as a whole, their employment in toxicity testing is most likely to continue for the foreseeable future.

Keywords: Toxicity testing, Hazardous effects, Animal species.

INTRODUCTION

The scientific field of toxicology is concerned with the characteristics, consequences, detection, diagnosis, and treatment of toxins or toxicants. In toxicology, it is crucial to understand how a dose affects the organism to which it is administered. For the creation of new medicines and the expansion of the therapeutic potential of already-existing compounds, toxicology screening is crucial. It results in better targeted pharmacological therapies with lower toxicity potential for the human body to treat various diseases including cancer. It aids in protecting people and the environment from the harmful effects of toxicants. [1]

Toxicity studies look into the potential compound's safety record. Additionally, they offer crucial details regarding the compound's absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) throughout the human body. Before a candidate drug may be given to the first human volunteer, it must undergo numerous different types of non-clinical toxicity tests; additional toxicity studies are then necessary before the medicine is given marketing authorization. Prior to being used on humans, newly created medications must undergo extensive toxicity testing. The majority of toxicity testing is done on experimental animals, and it identifies any potential risks that a test chemical is anticipated to cause as well as how it acts. [1]

In toxicity testing, employing animal models has many benefits. These benefits include the potential for a genetic makeup that is fully defined, their suitability to regulated exposure, controlled duration of exposure, and the potential for a thorough evaluation of all tissues after necropsy. The data gathered can be used to classify and mark compounds in commerce according to their level of danger. The goal of toxicity testing is to identify any potential hazardous consequences that a test chemical may have, not merely to determine how safe it is. Following the thalidomide disaster in the early 1960s, when thousands of infants were born all over the world with serious birth deformities, toxicity testing received a lot of attention. Many nations have decided to do toxicity and teratogenicity testing as a result of this tragedy. [2]

Toxicology testing used a variety of tests on many animal species over a lengthy period of time, constant monitoring of physiological and biochemical abnormalities, and a thorough post-mortem inspection at the conclusion of the trial to find any physical or histological abnormalities. Toxicology testing uses doses above the therapeutic range to identify the drug's harmful side effects. The goal of the current essay is to emphasise the value of toxicity testing in the creation of therapeutic medicines. The drug's toxic effects can be mild or so

severe as to prevent future compound development. Clinical analysis, autopsy analysis, haematological and haematochemical analysis, histological analysis, statistical presentation, and data interpretation are all used to assist toxicity studies. [3]

IMPORTANCE OF TOXICITY STUDIES

- ❖ A dose response curve to be established.
- ❖ To verify the safety of novel compounds before they are registered for widespread usage in industry or medical facilities as medications, food additives, or insecticides.
- ❖ To determine the mechanism or mode of action for a harmful impact that might have been noticed in prior investigations.
- ❖ To create epidemiological studies to explain population findings, such as the extensive research into the relationship between smoking and lung to certify innovative techniques for testing or research, notably those that use *in vitro* testing rather than animal testing. [4]

HISTORY [5]

The Father of Toxicology is Phillip von Hohenheim, better known as Paracelsus. He is given the most credit, nothing is without poison, yet everything is poisonous. Only the dosage renders something non-poisonous. Simply put, the dose determines the poison. Since his *Traite des poisons*, commonly known as *Toxicologie generalae*, published in 1813, Mathieu Orfila is regarded as the modern father of toxicology.

TYPES OF TOXICOLOGY [6]

TYPES	DEFINITIONS
Analytical Toxicology	It involves finding, identifying, and measuring foreign chemicals.
Applied Toxicology	The use of contemporary technology in the early detection of toxicants is a focus of applied toxicology.
Clinical Toxicology	The investigation of the detection and treatment of human poisoning.
Veterinary Toxicology	The study of identifying and treating animal poisoning, as well as the transfer of toxins from animals to people via animal products (Meat, Milk and other Foods).
Forensic Toxicology	In forensic toxicology, biological samples are examined for the presence of poisons, including pharmaceuticals.
Environment Toxicology	The investigation of the existence of several toxins and their metabolites
Industrial Toxicology	The investigation of the detrimental effects on people of chemicals used in production, workplace items, and waste products.
Reproductive & Developmental Toxicology	The examination of how chemicals or toxins affect the developing embryo and the reproductive system.
Immuno-Toxicology.	The investigation of toxins effects on the immune system.

Table: 1 Types of Toxicology

BRANCHES OF TOXICOLOGY [7-8]

The major areas of specialization are as follows:

- I. Mechanistic Toxicology (Basic Biology & Chemistry)
- II. Descriptive Toxicology (Testing).
- III. Regulatory Toxicology (Rule making & Compliance)

I) Mechanistic Toxicology

It is a field of toxicology that focuses on how chemicals affect living things in their cellular, biochemical, and molecular levels as well as how the biological system defends itself from these harmful effects. It seeks to

pinpoint the molecular processes that occur between the initial chemical exposure and the final manifestation of toxic damage in an organism.

- ★ The ability to prevent toxicity and create more aesthetically pleasing substances is enhanced by an understanding of a substance's toxicity mechanism.
- ★ Assist in the establishment of legally enforceable safe exposure limits for people by government authorities.
- ★ Laying the groundwork for innovative drug development and therapeutic approaches to human disease.

II) Descriptive Toxicology

It is directly involved with toxicity testing, which is typically conducted on animals and then compared to human results to offer data for safety assessments and regulatory needs. In reaction to exposure to a dangerous toxic chemical, it offers dose-response data. The results of the toxicity testing are often used to approve the usage of products and control the maximum concentrations that can be present in the environment.

The toxicity assessment commonly involves following steps:

- ★ Hazard identification
- ★ Dose-response assessment
- ★ Exposure assessment
- ★ Risk characterization

III) Regulatory Toxicology

The link between the field of toxicology and regulating bodies is the subject of this branch of toxicology. Toxicological principles and data from toxicity evaluation are used to make decisions about human health.

Main Focus Includes,

- ★ To alter the amount of chemical exposure in a way that is safe for health, the authority must decide on the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of a substance.
- ★ The authority may also create and severely enforce certain laws or regulatory requirements. Continuation.
- ★ According to the "no chemical is safe" principle of toxicology, all substances have the potential to be harmful based on their exposure, concentration, time, frequency, and nature.
- ★ In order to limit exposure concentration and maximise risk minimization, regulators create threshold doses. The governing bodies are the WHO, ICH, EPA, OECD, and FDA.

TYPES OF TOXICITY STUDIES [9]

Systemic toxicology studies

- ❖ Single-dose studies
- ❖ Repeated-dose studies

Reproductive toxicology studies

- ❖ Male fertility studies
- ❖ Female reproduction and developmental toxicology studies

Local Tolerance studies

Hypersensitivity studies

Genotoxicity studies

Carcinogenicity studies

SYSTEMIC TOXICITY STUDIES

Systemic toxicology studies examine the candidate compound's toxicity profile throughout all of the animal's tissues and organs. Studies in systemic toxicology may involve a single dosage or many doses.

REPRODUCTIVE TOXICITY STUDIES

Reproduction toxicity studies look at how the potential chemical affects an organism's capacity for normal development and reproduction. The following variables should be taken into account while these studies are carried out, as well as the population that will be exposed to the candidate compound,

- ❖ Men can participate in Phase I and II clinical trials prior to the conduct of the male fertility study because the repeated-dose toxicity studies evaluate the male reproductive organs; however, whenever possible, these studies should be conducted early in the process. Anyhow, before beginning large-scale or lengthy clinical trials (like Phase III trials), a male fertility research should be finished.
- ❖ If the pertinent repeated-dose toxicity studies (which include an assessment of the female reproductive organs) have been carried out, then clinical trials involving women who are not of childbearing potential, such as permanently sterile or postmenopausal women, can be conducted without reproduction toxicity studies.
- ❖ Reproduction toxicity studies must be carried out as soon as possible if women with the potential to carry children are recognised as a potential user group of the medication.

LOCAL TOLERANCE STUDIES

Studies on local tolerance look at how the substance affects the skin or eyes. Usually, the general toxicity investigations include these local toxicity assessments. A single dosage local tolerance study in one species is typically sufficient to support limited human administration through non-therapeutic methods, such as a single intravenous dose for determining absolute bioavailability.

GENOTOXICITY STUDIES

Genotoxicity studies, which examine how the potential drug affects chromosomes and genes, are typically required to validate claims of human safety. To support all single-dose clinical trials, it is deemed necessary to assess gene mutation. Before beginning Phase II clinical trials for multiple-dose clinical trials, a comprehensive battery of genotoxicity studies should be finished and an extra assessment of chromosomal damage in mammalian systems is required. Genotoxicity tests must be repeated if positive results are found, therefore this must be taken into attention

CARCINOGENICITY STUDIES

Assessments of the proposed compound's carcinogenicity look at how it affects the development of cancer. Studies on carcinogenicity are typically carried out to support the marketing of a new drug. To increase safety in clinical trials, carcinogenicity studies should be carried out if there is a serious reason for worry. In this situation, a longer-duration clinical trial with frequent monitoring can be conducted. Carcinogenicity testing is typically carried out post-approval for drugs used to treat severe conditions in adults or children, with the rationale that earlier patient access to the drugs outweighs any potential risks. However, the earlier these tests can be finished, the better.

TOXICOLOGY TESTING METHODS [10]

Toxicology studies are done by 3 methods.

1. *In-vivo* (using animals)
2. *In-vitro* (testing on isolated cells or tissues)
3. *In-silico* (computer simulation)

***In-vivo* studies**

In-vivo toxicity studies are conducted using animals to determine toxic effects. In-vivo toxicity studies include:

- Acute systemic toxicity (3 to 14 days)
- Sub-acute toxicity (14 to 30 days)
- Sub-chronic toxicity (longer than 30 days)

Acute systemic toxicity

Oral toxicity tests, skin toxicity tests, and inhalation toxicity tests are used to determine the short-term harmful effects that occur right away when a chemical is swallowed, absorbed through the skin, or breathed.

Sub-acute toxicity

They are done to look at potential side effects of a new medication after a two- to four-week treatment period. To establish the dose levels that will be used in subsequent subchronic and chronic toxicity studies, sub-acute toxicity studies are conducted.

Sub-chronic toxicity

Similar to shorter repeated dose toxicity study designs, the goal of sub-chronic and chronic toxicity research is to classify the dose-response relationship, identify target organs, and further test hypotheses about the therapeutic agent's mode of action.

***In-vitro* studies**

In-vitro toxicity studies are done using isolated organs and tissues cell cultures. *In-vitro* assays are developed using isolated cell components to evaluate biochemical and functional responses in order to discover the mechanism of action and innovation of various treatments.

Sources of tissues for in-vitro methods

- ❖ Rodents like rats and mice of both wild and transgenic types are used.
- ❖ Human tissues from neural progenitor cells from aborted fetuses and stem cell lines and also from cord blood derived stem cells.

***In-vitro* methods includes**

- ❖ *In-vitro* pyrogen test
- ❖ Embryonic stem cell test
- ❖ Repeated dose toxicity test
- ❖ Carcinogenicity test, etc

***In-silico* studies**

In-silico techniques relate to approaches or predictions that use computational procedures. *In silico* methods have the advantage of rapidly predicting a huge number of compounds in a high-throughput mode.

In-silico model includes various methods like

- ❖ Computer aided molecular drug design
- ❖ Quantitative Structure Activity Relationships (QSAR)
- ❖ Computer assisted learning
- ❖ Microfluidic chips
- ❖ DNA chips
- ❖ Computer or mathematical analysis

CONCLUSION

The goal of toxicity testing is to develop data that can ensure appropriate protection of public health from the adverse effects of exposures to environmental agents. Current approaches to toxicity testing rely primarily on observing adverse biologic responses in homogeneous groups of animals exposed to high doses of a test agent. Testing for toxicity is essential for determining the toxic effect and characterizing the test chemical. Animal investigations have shown that toxicity occurs in a similar way. Human incidence and severity. Animals are most likely to be used in toxicity testing for the foreseeable future due to the advantages they provide in analyzing a functioning full organism. The Present Review Conveys information about the Toxicology and its type, Importance, History, Branches, Types of Toxicity studies and Toxicological testing methods.

REFERENCES

1. Ernest Hodgson A., Text book on modern toxicology. Fourth edition. A John Wiley & Sons. Inc. Publication.2010:3-12.
2. Agrawal SS, Paridhavi M., Herbal drug technology. Universities press, India. 2007:607-614.
3. Klaassen CS. Principle of toxicology and treatment of poisoning. In: Parker BK, Blumenthal D, Buxton L (eds). Goodman & Gilman's; manual of pharmacology & therapeutics. McGraw Hill. 2008: 1115-1119.
4. Woolley A., A guide to practical toxicology, evaluation, prediction and risk. Second Edition, Informa HealthCare. New York, London. 2008.
5. Dhabal, S., Nandi, K., Jyoti. Sen. D., & Saha. D. (2022). Toxicology: It's Basic Instinct & Application in Forensic Field. Insights Herbal Med, 1(1), 23-30.
6. <https://anapath.ch/toxicology-and-its-components/>
7. Pani B., Textbook of Toxicology, first edition published by international publishing house Pvt. Ltd.
8. Stine.E.K., Principles of toxicology, Second edition CRC Press is an imprint of Taylor & Francis Group.
9. Gassama R., A Note on Toxicological Studies, Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research. 2021:13(10).
10. Parasuraman S., Toxicological screening, Journal of Pharmacology & Pharmacotherapeutics. 2011;2(2): 74-79.